

SPIRO-COMPOUNDS. PART III. SYNTHESIS OF CYCLO
HEXANE-SPIRO-CYCLOBUTANE DERIVATIVES BY
THE APPLICATION OF THE DIECKMANN
REACTION TO ESTERS OF THE TRICAR-
BALLYLIC SERIES.

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On the basis of the Baeyer's strain theory, the *cyclobutane* ring should be formed much more easily than the *cyclopropane* ring, and less easily than the *cyclohexane* and *cyclopentane* rings, but the methods which are used for the synthesis of three-, five- and six-membered rings break down wholly or partially in the case of the four-membered ring. The thermochemical data of Stohmann and Kleber (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1892, ii, 45, 475) are also at variance with the strain theory. This anomaly has been explained by Ingold (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 199, 305) by assuming that the angle between the two carbon valencies *via* polymethylene chain is 115.2° and not 109.5° as assumed by Baeyer.

The effect of *gem*-dialkyl grouping in promoting ring formation is evident from the work of Perkin and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 138), Kon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 810; 1922, 121, 513) and this has been explained on the valency deflection theory by Thorpe, Ingold and others (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1080).

The effect of *cyclohexane*, *methylcyclohexane*, *cyclopentane* and *gem*-dialkyl grouping, attached to a tricarballic acid residue, on the formation and stability of a spiro-*cyclobutane* ring has been studied and it has been observed that *cyclobutane* derivative could only be isolated in the case when it is combined with a *cyclohexane* ring. Freshly distilled *cyclohexanone* cyanohydrin is condensed with the sodium salt of ethyl cyanoacetate (*cf.* Dickens, Horton and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 128, 1830) and the sodium salt of ethyl 1-cyanocyclohexane-1-cyanoacetate (I), thus obtained, is allowed to react with ethyl bromoacetate to yield diethyl 1-cyanocyclohexane-1-cyanosuccinate (II). On hydrolysis the above ester yields 1-carboxycyclohexane-1-succinic acid (III). The corresponding ester yields diethyl *cyclohexane*-spiro-*cyclobutane*-2-one-3:4-dicarboxylate (IV) when heated with sodium in xylene. The yield of the keto-ester is very poor, barely reaching 1%

of the theoretical. This ester in alcoholic solution gives a reddish violet colouration with ferric chloride and when oxidised by means of nitric acid yields *cyclohexane-1:1*-dicarboxylic acid. Further corroborative proof is being collected in support of spiro-*cyclobutanone* structure.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

The products obtained from other ketone-cyanohydrins are tabulated below.

Cyanohydrins.	Condensation products.	Products after hydrolysis.	Esters of the tribasic acids.
4-Methylcyclohexanone-cyanohydrin	Diethyl 4-methyl-1-cyanocyclohexane-1-cyanosuccinate	4-Methylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic-1-succinic acid (A)	Triethyl 4-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1-succinate
2-Methylcyclohexanone-cyanohydrin	Diethyl 2-methyl-1-cyanocyclohexane-1-cyanosuccinate	2-Methylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic-1-succinic acid (B)	Triethyl 2-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1-succinate

Cyanohydrins.	Condensation products.	Products after hydrolysis.	Esters of the tribasic acids.
<i>cyclopentanone-cyanohydrin</i>	Diethyl 1-cyanocyclopentane-1-cyanosuccinate	<i>cyclopentane-1-carboxylic-1-succinic acid</i>	Triethyl <i>cyclopentane-1-carboxylate-1-succinate</i> (C)
Acetone-cyanohydrin	Diethyl 2-methyl-2 : 3-dicyanobutane-3 : 4-dicarboxylate	<i>αα</i> -Dimethyltricarballic acid (F)	Triethyl <i>αα</i> -dimethyltricarballic acid (D)
3-Methylcyclohexanone-cyanohydrin	Diethyl 3-methyl-1-cyanocyclohexane-1-cyanosuccinate	3-Methylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic-1-succinic acid (E)	Triethyl 3-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1-succinate

Triethyl 4-methyl-*cyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1-succinate* undergoes ring closure in presence of sodium in xylene to yield 4'-methylcyclohexane-spirocyclobutane-2-one-3:4-dicarboxylate. In alcoholic solution it gives a reddish violet colouration with ferric chloride.

Attempt has also been made with the esters (C and D) to effect the ring-closure but no definite product could be isolated.

The acid (F) is known as the oxidation product of many terpene compounds (Tiemann and Semmler, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1349; Gardner and Cockburn, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1898, 73, 708; Jagelki, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 1509; Baeyer, *ibid.*, 1896, 29, 2792). The synthetic method of preparing this acid is that due to Haller and Blank (*Compt. rend.*, 1900, 131, 19) who obtained it by hydrolysing the condensation product of ethyl cyanosuccinate and ethyl α -bromoisobutyrate (Barthe, *Compt. rend.*, 1897, 125, 182) by means of hydrochloric acid. Other synthetic methods are those due to Bome and Spränkling (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 81, 49) and Clemo and Welch (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2621).

Compounds (A, B and E) may occur in two or more forms. Experiments are in progress to separate them.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Diethyl 1-cyanocyclohexane-1-cyanosuccinate.—To a well-cooled solution of freshly distilled *cyclohexanone-cyanohydrin* (186 g.) in absolute alcohol (186 c.c.), a suspension of ethyl sodiocyanoacetate, obtained from ethyl cyanoacetate (168 g.), sodium (33 g.) and alcohol (500 c.c.), was

gradually added with vigorous shaking. The mixture after being kept in ice for 6 hours and at room temperature for 3 days was mixed with ethyl bromoacetate (280 g.) and after the initial reaction had abated was boiled under reflux until it was neutral to litmus (8 hours). The mixture was filtered and the filtrate diluted with water and extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with water, dried and the ether removed. It distilled as a viscous liquid, b.p. 200-205°/7 mm., yield 170 g. (Found : C, 62.6; H, 7.2 $C_{16}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires C, 62.7; H, 7.19 per cent).

1-Carboxycyclohexane-1-succinic Acid.—The foregoing ester (20 g) was mixed with sulphuric acid (70 %, 120 c.c.) and boiled under reflux for 12 hours. The condenser was removed from time to time to allow the alcohol formed to escape. The solution was then diluted with water and extracted with ether, and the ethereal solution was treated with sodium carbonate. On acidification of the carbonate solution a product was obtained which was heated on the water-bath with a solution of caustic alkali (15 %) for 3-4 hours. The alkaline solution was then acidified and extracted with ether. After removing ether the product was kept in a desiccator when it solidified. It crystallised from ether, m. p. 187° (decomp.), yield 10 g. (Found : C, 54.7; H, 6.5. $C_{11}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 54.1; H, 6.5 per cent).

Triethyl cyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1-succinate was obtained in an almost quantitative yield from the acid by the alcohol vapour method. In a typical experiment the acid (20 g.), absolute alcohol (60 c.c.), concentrated sulphuric acid (6 c.c.), 3 litres of vaporised alcohol (3-4 hours) gave 22 g. of the ester, b.p. 174-76°/6 mm. (Found : C, 62.1; H, 8.4. $C_{17}H_{28}O_6$ requires C, 62.1; H, 8.5 per cent).

Diethyl cyclohexane-spiro-cyclobutane-2-one-3:4-dicarboxylate (IV).—A mixture of the foregoing ester (30 g.) and granulated sodium (4.3 g.) in dry xylene (150 c.c.) was heated on an oil-bath at about 150° for $\frac{3}{4}$ hour. The sodium gradually dissolved and a red jelly filled the flask. Frequent shaking was necessary to prevent local overheating, leading to decomposition, and 50 c.c. of xylene after 20-30 minutes were added to prevent the mass from becoming too solid. When cooled the reaction mixture was decomposed with ice and ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid. The products of six such operations were combined. The acid aqueous layer was separated from the xylene solution and extracted with ether, which was added to the xylene solution. After washing with water this solution was treated with sodium carbonate solution. After washing with water and drying over sodium sulphate, the ether-xylene solution was fractionated. The ester was obtained as a pale yellow

oil, b p. 178-80°/6 mm. (Found : C, 63.1; H, 7.4. $C_{15}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 63.8; H, 7.8 per cent).

Oxidation of cyclohexane-spiro-cyclobutane-2-one-3:4-dicarboxylate.—The keto-ester (1.5 g.) was warmed with an excess of concentrated nitric acid until most of the red fumes disappeared. The resulting solution was then boiled for a few minutes and finally evaporated to dryness. The residue was treated with water and again evaporated; the semi-solid mass, thus obtained, was left on a porous plate and after crystallisation from water the *cyclohexane-1:1-dicarboxylic acid* melted at 176° (decomp.) (lit. m. p. 176°).

Almost identical conditions were employed in the preparation of the compounds described in the following table.

	Products.	B.p. or M.p.	Formula.	Analysis.		Yield.
				Found.	Calc.	
(1) 4-Methyl- <i>cyclohexanone</i> cyanohydrin (190 g.)	Diethyl 4-methyl- <i>cyclohexane-1-cyano-1-cyanosuccinate</i>	203°-210°/6 mm. m.p. 90° cryst. from ether	$C_{17}H_{24}O_4N_2$	C, 64.1, H, 7.5 N, 8.8	63.7; 7.5 8.75	150 g.
Product of hydrolysis (20 g. of cyanoester)	4-Methyl- <i>cyclohexane-1-carboxylic-1-succinic acid</i>	m.p. 188° cryst. from ether	$C_{12}H_{18}O_6$	C, 56.5 H, 7.0	55.8 6.9	12 g.
Ester	Triethyl 4-methyl- <i>cyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1-succinate</i>	178°-80°/5 mm.	$C_{18}H_{26}O_6$	63.0 8.7	63.1 8.7	Quantitative
Dieckmann reaction product	4'-Methyl- <i>cyclohexane-spiro-cyclobutane-2-one-3:4-dicarboxylate</i>	177°-85°/5 mm.	$C_{16}H_{24}O_6$	64.1 8.4	64.8 8.1	About 1 per cent.
(2) 2-Methyl- <i>cyclohexanone</i> cyanohydrin (180 g.)	Diethyl 2-methyl- <i>cyclohexane-1-cyano-1-cyanosuccinate</i>	200°-208°/6 mm.	$C_{17}H_{24}O_4N_2$	64.0 7.6	63.7 7.5	50 g.
Product of hydrolysis (20 g. of cyanoester)	2-Methyl- <i>cyclohexane-1-carboxylic-1-succinic acid</i>	No definite isomer could be isolated	$C_{12}H_{18}O_6$	56.4 7.2	55.8 6.9	10 g.
Ester	Triethyl 2-methyl- <i>cyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1-succinate</i>	175°-76°/4 mm.	$C_{18}H_{26}O_6$	63.3 8.7	63.1 8.7	Quantitative

	Products.	B.p. or M.p.	Formula.	Analysis.		Yield.
				Found.	Calc.	
(3) 3-Methylcyclohexanone cyanohydrin (180 g.)	Diethyl 3-methylcyclohexane-1-cyano-1-cyanosuccinate	200-205°/6 mm.	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₂	C, 64.0 H, 7.7	63.7 7.5	120 g.
Product of hydrolysis (20 g. of cyano ester)	3-Methyl-cyclohexane-1-carboxylic-1-succinic acid	No definite isomer could be isolated	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ O ₆	56.5 7.3	55.8 6.9	10 g.
Ester	Triethyl 3-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1-succinate	178°/5 mm.	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O ₆	63.4 8.6	63.1 8.7	Quantitative
(4) cyclopentanone cyanohydrin (186 g.)	Diethyl cyclopentane-1-cyano-1-cyanosuccinate	197°-203°/7 mm.	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂	62.0 6.9	61.6 6.8	120 g.
Product of hydrolysis (20 g. of cyano ester)	cyclopentane-1-carboxylic-1-succinic acid	m.p. 159° cryst. from ether	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₆	52.75 6.1	52.15 6.08	11 g.
Ester	Triethyl cyclopentane-1-carboxylate-1-succinate	173°-75°/7 mm.	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₆	61.1 8.1	61.1 8.2	Quantitative
(5) Acetone cyanohydrin (90 g.)	Diethyl 2-methyl-2 : 3-dicyanobutane-3 : 4-dicarboxylate	180°-82°/6 mm.	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂	58.7 6.6	58.6 6.7	50 g.
Product of hydrolysis (20 g. of cyano ester)	αα-Dimethyltricarballic acid	m.p. 156° cryst. from dilute HCl	C ₈ H ₁₂ O ₆	46.8 5.8	47.06 5.8	8 g.
Ester	Triethyl αα-dimethyltricarballicylate	160°/5 mm	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O ₆	58.3 8.5	58.3 8.3	Quantitative

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